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MARKETING COMMUNICATION AND ITS RELEVANCE

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Anotation. *The article is intended to highlight the importance of marketing communication and how it plays an important role in promoting a good product to your branding. F. Kotler, advertising, communication tools, 4p, brand, marketing channels, sales promotion, personal sales, direct marketing, sales, communication path, sponsorship, announcement, distribution.*

Keywords. *Marketing, communion, advertising, brand, message, Buyer and seller Introduction*

МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ КОММУНИКАЦИИ И ИХ АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ.

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Аннотация. *Цель статьи – подчеркнуть важность маркетинговых коммуникаций и то, как они играют важную роль в продвижении хорошего продукта под вашим брендом. Ф. Котлер, реклама, инструменты коммуникации, 4p, бренд, каналы сбыта, стимулирование сбыта, персональные продажи, прямой маркетинг, продажи, путь коммуникации, спонсорство, анонс, распространение.*

Ключевые слова. *Маркетинг, общение, реклама, бренд, сообщение, Покупатель и продавец. Введение*

Introduction. "Communion", which first appeared in the 20th century in the scientific literature, has different interpretations. Nowadays, the social essence of this concept and its interpretation associated with its psychologic components are widespread. The term "Communion", which first appeared in the 20th century in the scientific literature, has different interpretations. Nowadays, the social essence of this concept and its interpretation associated with its psychologic components are widespread.

According to the definition given in the large encyclopedic dictionary, communion (derived from Lot, comunicatio - comunico - general I do, tie, FC communicate) is:

1) communication path, connection of one place with another:

2) communication, the transfer of information from one person to another is mainly a form of self-knowledge of knowledge with the help of language and interaction in the processes of labor activity (less often with the help of other sign systems). Many researchers distinguish the important perception of Communications separately - this is the transfer and exchange of information in order to influence it in society.

Thus, Communications, including marketing Communications, are the system in which these interactions are carried out, both interaction and variety in our case- the co-operation of communication isullar, which allows the creation, transmission and reception of marketing information, and marketing communication denotes the joint use of different marketing channels and tools. Marketing communication channels focus on how the main reach is delivered to the market desired by the business itself or to the market in general. He is also responsible for the internal communications of the organization.

Marketing means of communion are the following; advertising, sponsorship of sales promotion. PR (public releushiz), direct marketing, covers niche vendors.

Marketing communication consists of a marketing mix consisting of 4p. Consists of 4p-Product, Price, Place, promotions. The number of P's in place can also be 7 or more. Because nowadays, 4P itself is scarce, to which People, Physical evidence, process as an addition. P's help to gather a target audience in marketing. Therefore, it is currently switched from 4P to 7p model. What is marketing communication in itself actually for and what task does it perform?

The marketing communion process allows the public to promote a brand or generate insight and have a clear idea of what a brand offers. For example you haven't used Areal but you know that it's washing powder. Brand reporting is the first stage, and the postponement consists of finding buyers in the invasions by showing the advantages of the brand from existing competitors in the market. Achieved success

F. In Kotler's amshkhur textbook on marketing, marketing communiqés with which firms inform consumers directly or indirectly about their goods and shopping centers are described as tools that try to convince and remind.

Main part. Modern marketing requires much more than creating a commodity that meets the customer's needs and setting a price that corresponds to it and ensuring its openness to targeted customers. Firms can make a communication with their customers. In doing so, there should be nothing

accidental in the content of the communiqués, otherwise the magnitude of the communication costs incurred and the amount of profit the firm receives will be reduced due to the damage to the firm.

Management-marketing activities provide information about business strategy and decision making. Marketing information and concepts help with product development, pricing, and distribution decisions.

The market system, also known as the free market system, is an economic system in which the distribution of prices, production and goods and services is determined by the forces of supply and demand. In the market system, individuals and enterprises make economic decisions based on their personal interests, the interaction of buyers and sellers in the market determines the distribution of resources, the distribution of goods and services. The market system is based on the principle of competition, which encourages enterprises to produce high-quality goods and services at competitive prices to attract buyers. The market system is based on the principle of competition, which encourages enterprises to produce high-quality goods and services at competitive prices to attract buyers. Competition also encourages innovation and efficiency as businesses seek to improve their products and processes to gain a competitive advantage in the market. The market system relies on the price mechanism to allocate resources and determine the value of goods and services. Prices are determined by the forces of supply and demand, and they reflect the wishes of consumers and the costs of production. In a market system, prices serve as a signal for economic decision-making and efficient allocation of resources.

Marketing plays a decisive role in the market system by facilitating the exchange of goods and services between buyers and sellers. Through market research and analysis, businesses can identify customer needs and desires and develop products and services that meet these needs. Marketing also helps businesses stand out from competitors and bring the value of their products and services to customers.

Marketing plays a key role in creating and supporting competition in the market system. By promoting their products and services, businesses can attract customers and gain market share. The competition between businesses encourages them to innovate and improve their products and services to meet the changing needs of customers. Marketing also plays an important role in determining the price of goods and services in the market system. By analyzing production costs and demand for their products and services, businesses can set prices that reflect the value of their offerings and consumer preferences.

Marketing is an important function in the market system, as it helps enterprises to identify and meet the needs of customers, differentiate from competitors, facilitate the exchange of goods and services in the market. Through effective marketing, enterprises can create and support competition, update and improve their products and services, effectively allocate resources in the market system.

Marketing plays an important role in the market system by facilitating the exchange of goods and services between buyers and sellers. Marketing activities such as market research and analysis, product development and Design, Promotion and advertising, sales and distribution help businesses identify and meet customer needs, differentiate from competitors, and convey the value of their offerings.

Marketing also plays a decisive role in creating and supporting competition in the market system. Through effective marketing, businesses can attract customers and gain market share, leading to innovation, improved products and services, and efficient resource allocation.

Marketing also helps to determine prices in the market system. By analyzing production costs and demand for their products and services, businesses can set prices that reflect the value of their offerings and consumer preferences.

Communication between Marketing and other business functions:

Marketing is an important business function that interacts with and affects other business functions. For example:

Finance-marketing activities require financial resources, such as funds for market research, product development, and advertising.

The application of modern information technologies to automate the activities of small and medium-sized economic objects, government bodies, transport, construction, trade and other economic objects carries out information systems on the basis of "electronic offices", that is, distributed databases and local computing networks that combine separate automated workplaces.

Automated training systems. The use of Information Technology in the training and training of personnel leads to the creation of automated training systems (AOTS), which are used in training processes in all branches of the continuing education system.

The introduction of information technologies into the bodies of the God-administrative management leads to the God information systems (letters). They create to provide the analysis and management functions of local government bodies and management.

The activities of the holy system are aimed at qualitatively carrying out management work in the region, forming a report, providing quick information to state and local oxen bodies.

In accordance with the structural-territorial bodies of management, the following systems are distinguished:

- information systems of autonomous republics, regions;
- information system of urban management;
- the information system of the administrative district.

According to the level of quality, information systems are divided into the following classes: information search engine (AQT); information reference system (AAT); text processing information system (MQAT); data processing system (MQT); information management system (ICT); decision – making system (QQQT); expert systems (ET). Information-search engine. Carries out a search for documents, secondary documents (e.g. abstracts), the name of documents or the full text of addresses, which can be stored in or out of the EHM. In one case or another, the EXM stores a formalized statement of documents that have received the name of the search image and whose summary is described. Information consumers who want to find a document on the topic they need will send a request to Tazim. According to the search result, information is provided about the full text of the described documents or about the correct, incorrect, insufficient, level of reliability of the requested expenses.

The information and reference system is designed in many ways to provide, collect and store information of economic, technical or technological content at the request of users. It can be said that the information and reference system is aimed at working with digital or text-concretized data. Determines how to present the result according to the type and form of the request. Survey results can be issued in the form of a standard reference, or can be designed in an optional view during processing of a user's request according to their wishes. The text processing system (MQT) is designed to edit, store, and reproduce texts (letter, article, abstract, command, and hakazo) directly to the user. Ijallangan. Ma the ' data processing system (MQIT) is designed to calculate data on formalized algorithms of calculations in EHM. These recommendations are given to the discretion of the decision-making person. Various mathematical models are placed on the basis of an advisory (board) information system, similar to real reality, that is, a process in an object or in a control system.

The decision-making system (QQQT) is distinguished by the fact that the decision option developed in the EHM is made to fulfill. At the moment, the

production system (automated system of control of technological processes dispatcher control system) automatically carries out the execution of decisions made by the EHM through appropriate enforcement mechanisms

Expert systems – in addition to the database in EHM-are characterized by the presence of two more-knowledge and a database of goals. Databases (MB) have a quantitative formal description of the control system and object; the knowledge base (BB) Maintains a statement of informal semantic representations of external muxit, some qualitative description of objects, relations between them, possible actions, States, abstractions, streotypes. The base of goals has a tasvur on interconnected goals, younger goals, methods and means of reaching them, characteristic of the objects to be modeled. Such systems are very relevant in creative, R & D, design, management processes.

The growing flow of information in modern society, the diversity of Information Technologies, the complication of issues solved on the computer put a number of tasks before the user of these technologies. The question arises of the choice of the necessary options and the transfer of decision-making work from person to person. One of the ways to solve this task is to consider the creation and use of expert systems. The expert, based on himself, analyzes the conditions and identifies relatively useful information, gives rise to the most optimal ways to make a decision, abandoning unsecured paths.

The expert system uses a knowledge base that represents a specific subject area.

The expert system is a set of methods and tools for collecting and applying knowledge in certain subject areas. The expert system achieves an even higher effect for the abundance of alternatives when choosing a decision, relying on the high-quality experience of specialists. When drawing up a strategy, it evaluates new factors and analyzes their effects.

Expert systems are based on the use of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is understood as the ability of the computer system in relation to mental actions. Often in this, the ability associated with human thinking is realized.

Conclusion.

Expert systems can be considered as a class of Information Systems. It has a data and knowledge base that can tah-lil and edit data regardless of the user's consent, analyze the decision, perform analytical-classification tasks. In particular, expert systems are able to divide incoming information into groups, draw conclusions, identify, diagnose, teach prediction, comment, etc.

In conclusion, marketing communication is a very important factor that allows the firm to create products, produce, Price, enter the market, find haridor, re-establish relations with haridors, from the sale of products. Marketing communication is a huge process that splits into many networks. For example, advertising, direct sales, direct marketing are among them. But the main goal of marketing communication is to introduce the product to the client, keep the connection and remind him. Because, having an understanding of the product, hairdo can buy when he needs it, even if he does not buy it at that time. Because a note is made using marketing communication. Therefore, marketing communication is relevant and it should be studied in depth.

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